

THE MAIN TYPES AND FORMS OF EMPLOYMENT OF THE POPULATION AND STATE POLICY IN ITS IMPLEMENTATION

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Abstract. *In this article, the implementation of the right to work and free choice of work, property status, professional position, faith and membership of public associations, as well as aspects of employees' work, support and encouragement of people's work and entrepreneurial initiatives, and productive conditions that provide decent conditions for working and living in them and support for the development of creative work ability was considered.*

Keywords: *population, work, community, conditions, ability, development, market, employment.*

Introduction. In the conditions of the transition to the market economy, the problem of employment and its organizers acquires a new meaning in both theoretical and practical aspects. is distributed.

The labor market ensures the employment of the economically active population, involvement in the production and service sector. It facilitates the employee's transition to a more suitable workplace. Through the labor market, enterprises are provided with workers of the required quantity and required quality.

The labor market shows what personnel, specialists, professions are in demand, and which of them are surplus. This is an actual problem for many countries. Its solution means the creation of an effective economy capable of ensuring the social development of society.

Employment is a set of measures and actions aimed at expanding the demand for the labor force (providing the scope, conditions and forms of their involvement in useful activities, formation, distribution, use, release, retraining and redistribution of employed employees). can be described.

Within this concept, fully intelligent (rational) and productive employment are distinguished. "Full" employment is the social and economic realization of the totality and obligation of work in socialism.

Taking into account the above-mentioned shortcomings, the level of full employment will be adjusted to the market economy. The interpretation of the highest level of involvement of the working population in the social economy is also changing.

Full employment can be achieved at any level of attracting the population, in which it should be consistent with meeting the needs of the population for jobs, and the offered jobs should be economically reasonable (effective). In this case, an economically appropriate workplace is understood as a workplace that allows a person to achieve high labor productivity and have a salary that is sufficient for him and his family to live well, at the same time, this workplace does not harm his health and human dignity. should not hit the ground.

Thus, full employment does not mean the involvement of all able-bodied citizens in the field of professional work. A person has the right to choose one of the spheres of socially useful employment (professional labor in the national economy, household, etc.) according to his desire. However, the main regulatory type of activity is employment with professional work that brings income, increases the well-being of a person and ensures its development, and reflects achievements in the field of labor productivity and social efficiency of community development. This means that this proportion of employment fully corresponds to the interests of increasing production efficiency, the results of its acceleration, the interests of scientific and technical development to increase labor productivity, and also creates favorable conditions for raising a healthy generation, raising highly qualified, well-educated workers. , such employment ratio is considered the most acceptable (optimal).

Full employment that meets all of the above conditions can be called productive employment. In this, we are based on the fact that productive employment is not the same thing as productive work. Effective work is a component of productive employment. Ultimately, full and productive employment is an integral part.

If full employment is achieved with economically unsuitable jobs or jobs that do not provide a decent livelihood, if it contradicts the level of professional qualifications and education of employees or tasks in the national economy, if it prevents the training of qualified personnel and normal demographic development of the population, such work employment does not contribute to universal values and cannot be considered positive.

People's need for socially necessary employment and the possibility of its implementation should be systematically regulated. The purpose of this is to provide human activity, improve conditions, and ensure efficient functioning of the economy.

Employment status is determined for a part of labor resources participating in socially useful activities. These are a group of people who offer labor for the production of goods and services for the purpose of earning income, as well as a group of people who do not directly generate monetary income even if they participate in socially beneficial activities, or a group of people who generate income directly related to the production of goods and services.

The first group includes citizens working in cooperatives, joint-stock companies, and the private sector employed in the public sector of the economy, and the second group includes students who receive education separated from production, and employees of the armed forces of the republic. Thus, the employed population includes citizens who work for hire, including full-time or part-time working days (weeks) for a fee, as well as those who have a paid job approved by the relevant contract, are absent from work due to illness or vacation.

Self-employed persons, including entrepreneurs and farmers, persons serving in military units, students are also included in the category of employed persons. People who are looking for a job, changing their job, temporarily not working and not studying while separated from work, seasonality of work Due to this, the population temporarily unemployed belongs to the economically active unemployed population. Persons with the status of unemployed are also included in the population of economically active people who are not employed.

Employment relations are related to economic, demographic and social processes. The economic content of employment is represented by the work that forms and develops the individual, with the opportunity to ensure a decent life for the employee with his own work and to achieve an increase in the efficiency of social production.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process

Analysis and results. The efficiency of employment can be described by indicators that reflect the ideology of state development, and they are formed under the influence of the growth of social labor productivity. First of all, these are the proportions of distribution of labor resources of the society based on their participation in socially useful activities. They show at what level of labor productivity the population's need for work is satisfied and in what ways full employment is achieved.

Because the higher the productivity of social labor, the more material conditions for high incomes of employees are collected, the technical and organizational improvement of the labor field, the improvement of personnel qualifications, the consideration of the specific aspects of the working and living conditions of different groups of the population are ensured. the second feature is the level of employment of the able-bodied population in the social economy.

Statistically, it is reflected by the ratio of the population engaged in income-generating professional work to the entire working population. Economically, this indicator reflects the need for public sector employees and the population's need for jobs. From a general theoretical point of view, unemployment reflects the incompatibility of labor supply and demand for it in the economy, their inconsistency in terms of quantity, structure (territorial, professional qualifications, etc.).

This is one of the important permanent features of social and economic life in the conditions of the formation and existence of the labor market. Real assessment of unemployment and its measurement is carried out in accordance with the recommendations of the International Labor Organization and taking into account the established experience of labor relations.

In Uzbekistan, the unemployed are people aged 16 and over, who are not currently employed or gainfully employed, are looking for work, and are ready to start work. The main danger of hidden types of unemployment and informal employment, in addition to the possibility of transitioning to open unemployment, is the violation of work ethics, the loss of skills of the workforce, the loss of interest and skills in the profession, and the impoverishment of a certain part of people who are not currently needed by society. In addition, excess in enterprises staff retention may cause an unjustified increase in product costs and inflation. The third feature of employment efficiency consists of the distribution structure of workers by sectors of the national economy.

It is possible to stimulate economic activity and, as a result, to expand employment, through state intervention in the economy through various methods aimed at increasing the demand for payment.

According to the theory of Keynes, the decisive role in this will belong to the promotion and regulation of private investments by the state, and the budget policy covering the areas of taxation, debt and spending of public funds. Expanding investment means increasing production and, therefore, employment. A lower indicator is considered to be inconsistent with the "normal operation of the labor market" and violates the optimal ratio of labor supply and demand.

Table 1 shows the change of the working population and the employed population in Samarkand region in 2018-2022. In 2018, 60% of the population had the ability to work, and in 2022, this indicator was 56.1%. The rate of natural growth of the population increased by 4% over five years, while the number of the population with the ability to work increased by only 0.7%.

2018-2022 status of the relationship between population, working population and employed population in Samarkand region

Table 1

Years	Total population, thousand people	Growth rate compared to last year, %	Working population, thousand people	Growth rate compared to last year, %	Employed population, thousand people	Growth rate compared to last year, %
2018	3651.7	-	2183.9	-	1 523.1	-
2019	3720.1	101.9	2206.6	101.0	1463.3	96.1
2020	3798.9	102.1	2228.0	101.0	1 455.8	99.5
2021	3877.4	102.1	2245.9	100.8	1 418.3	97.4
2022	4031.3	104.0	2262.6	100.7	1 441.3	101.6

In the conditions of economic liberalization, the state conducts a consistent socio-economic policy to provide employment to the population and eliminate unemployment. Because increasing employment is an important factor in developing the national economy, raising the standard of living of the population, and joining the ranks of highly developed countries. The implementation of state policy in the field of employment is one of the main social tasks of the reforms implemented in Uzbekistan.

The state policy in the field of employment of the population in Uzbekistan is based on the following principles:

- in exercising the right to work and freely choose a job, all citizens are subject to gender, age, race, nationality, language, social origin, property status, professional position, religion, belief, and membership of public associations, as well as aspects of employees' work and the results of their work. ensure equal opportunities regardless of other circumstances;
- to support and encourage people's work and entrepreneurial initiatives, to help develop productive and creative work skills that provide decent conditions for working and living in them;
- Voluntary work;
- providing social guarantees in the field of employment and ensuring protection of the population from unemployment;
- encouraging employers to maintain existing jobs and create new jobs for citizens who are in dire need of social protection and have difficulty finding work;
- coordination of activities in the field of employment with other directions of social and economic policy;
- mutual cooperation of state bodies, trade unions, employee representative bodies and employers in the development, implementation and monitoring of employment measures for the population;
- interstate cooperation in solving the problems of providing employment to the population

The employment policy, which is a component of the reforms being carried out in the republic, provides for the achievement of the following main goals:

- acceleration of the process of redistribution of vacated employees on the basis of stimulation of structural restructuring;
- intensively attracting the unemployed to work;
- providing employment to every job seeker.

To achieve these goals, the following measures are implemented by the state:

1. If unemployment acquires a periodic character, the state uses budgetary, fiscal, credit-monetary tools, that is:

- spends more money on production to increase employment;
- reduces the interest rates of loans and credits to increase the interest of the entrepreneur;
- reduces taxes on producers and consumers.

2. When frictional and hidden types of unemployment increase, the state:

- re-trains;
- expands the education system;
- expands information about vacancies;
- increases investments aimed at the development of labor market infrastructure.

Ways to influence the employment of the population include:

- direct (administrative) methods - legal procedure;
- indirect (economic) methods - financial, monetary, fiscal policy.

There are the following types of state influence on the employment of the population:

- passive influence - social assistance to the unemployed population;
- active influence - measures to stimulate the supply of labor, stimulate the demand for labor,

coordinate demand and supply (providing information, consulting services, providing advice in the professional field, developing employment programs for less competitive groups of the population, etc.), providing assistance to regions - events and so on.

The state's policy of active influence is based on the state of regional labor markets. If there is a labor surplus (surplus) in the region, and the supply is higher than the demand, then the state conducts a policy of reducing the supply of labor and stimulating the increase in demand for it. On the contrary, if there is a labor shortage (deficit) in the region, then the state determines specific measures to increase the supply of labor and reduce the demand for it.

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